

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 1

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARDIYA J. BALAHIM, LPT, ED.D

Associate Professor II

Sulu State College

mardiyabalahim69@gmail.com

“PAIN”

In every disappointment in life,
Facing it feels unreal.
Sacrifice becomes the only way,
to confront what I cannot heal.

Prayers and small fulfillment
these are my quiet happiness.
I have encountered countless trials,
but despite them all,
bravery is the weapon I carry.

I ignore the pain, and endure the weight,
And a different me emerges,
steadfast, unshakeable, awake.

Pain has pulled me close to death,
yet never broke me into pieces.
For my priority is above it.

And now I hold a precious life,
A life I choose, a life I embrace.

